

THE ROLE OF THE FAMILY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CHILD'S SPIRITUALITY

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Annotation: This article discusses the value of child rearing over gold and the role of the family in the development of a child's spirituality. Enriched with sufficient information on child rearing and spirituality. The role of the family in the development of a child's spirituality plays a huge role. For a child's future, a parent should pay much more strong attention to his or her child because the spirituality, culture, behavior, efforts, practical and theoretical way of life in his or her life are devoted to him.

Keywords: The way to a child's heart, education and upbringing, the nature of a child, the worldview of a child, a healthy child, a perfect generation.

LOG IN

"The child is almighty, and his decency is dearer than him," said our wise people. The child was born into a family where his pure and pure feelings, first of all, his concepts and imaginations of life were formed in the family. It is only natural for a family to find the foundation of sacred concepts, such as goodness and goodness, superiority and love, or-sad and bad, that determine a child's character, nature, and worldliness. That is why respect for the parents who arise in the same family environment, a deep understanding of the life-threatening duty of debt to them, constitutes the essence of human qualities and family relationships, the spiritual world of the family.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Years of scientific observations and research show that a person receives 70% of all the information he receives during his or her lifetime under the age of five [1]. Given that a child's mind is formed mainly at the age of 5-7, it is during this time that the first frogs of spirituality begin to manifest themselves in his heart by the influence of the family environment. It is during this period that a child begins to understand and understand everything good and bad, and like a printed piece of paper, his innocent mind can absorb all the events in the family, around him, and the impressions of their time. His love and respect for his parents, grandparents, and mothers and his attitude toward the environment surrounding him are improved day by day.

RESEARCH METADOLODY

The main thing in family law is the personal legal relationship between all family members. It is they, for the most part, that determine the content of property family law relations. Based on this, it should be concluded that the content of family law relations includes the rights and obligations of absolutely all subjects of such legal relations. The specification of rights and obligations, their scope are contained in the norms of family law governing family relations, such as marriage and its dissolution, personal and property relations between partners, alimony relations between all family members, between parents and children, between adoptive parents and adopted children, etc.

It is also important to pay attention to seemingly small issues in child rearing [2]. When a person lives, he must acquire knowledge and improve himself. Because you like the end of knowledge, and even if you spend your whole life, you will not be able to reach its end. So seek knowledge to your last breath rather than spending time on idle things. In order not to make a mistake in the issue of family upbringing, it would have been appropriate to first build the spiritual climate in any household on the basis of mutual respect, decency, human relationships, and to develop a family and society that sets an example for their children. From this point of view, it is only natural for all of us to be attracted to many remarkable families who still live in our country with such

beautiful moral criteria and raise their sons and daughters in this spirit. The Uzbek people have long been distinguished by their childhood and family life. Of course, bringing up our forefathers from a young age on the basis of national upbringing, morality, and high spirituality has always been a major factor for us.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Child rearing is one of the most important tasks. A child's heart can be likened to a clean, delicate nipple. How it is cared for is shaped like that, bent to the bent side. If a child learns good and grows up in goodness, he will prosper as a perfect man in the world. Of course, this is also influenced by parent coaches and the environment. But when a child is neglected, grows up in a bad state, his upbringing becomes complicated, and a person who has not found his place in society is formed. Parents are also responsible for raising such a child.

The next crisis comes in the seventh year of the partners' life together. These two significant dates are considered one of the most difficult periods of family life. The child is already old enough to be sent to kindergarten. A woman, feeling like a driven horse who has seen nothing but the kitchen, is eager to go to work. It doesn't matter which one, the main thing is that you don't sit at home. However, household chores remain a heavy burden on her shoulders. With employment, she will have to combine not only life, caring for her husband and child, but also her new job. At this stage, it is the strong half that should look for a compromise.

Ten years of marriage are characterized by an even life, intimate and sincere relationships, communication, work. At this stage, the woman who initiates the divorce often becomes a spouse who is already fed up and a little tired of each other. Most husbands complain that their wives have ceased to share their hobbies with him, began to ignore romantic impulses, which leads to the emergence of connections on the side

Therefore, parents should pay attention to every aspect when raising their child. It is necessary to teach your child goodness, such as eating etiquette, dress culture, father's determination in the family, rules of conversation, and love for the book. A

child is the most precious blessing. It is in our own hands for children to grow up to be perfect people and to be blind in the land [3]. "A wise thought understands that there is a family in this bright world where there is life. When there is a family, there is a precious blessing called a child.

CONCLUSIONS

As long as there is a child, mankind will always live with good desires. " "There will be nothing big or small in the family, and family relationships, which seem to be the simplest, will also affect the child. Honesty, sincerity, loyalty, and sweetness are among the necessary means of life in a child's perfection." Today, our young people play a vital role in bringing our country to a greater peak. Youth - The future of Uzbekistan! The family plays a vital role in educating young people in all aspects of their mature spirituality.

Available literature

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